

TRACING SUCCESS: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON THE EMPLOYABILITY OF SAN CARLOS COLLEGE (2019-2021)

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Abstract. This tracer study assesses the employability of San Carlos College graduates (2019-2021), aiming to align educational programs with the evolving job market. It evaluates the relevance of coursework to graduates' employment, identifies areas for curriculum enhancement, and explores factors influencing successful entry into the job market. The study also measures graduates' self-perceived skills, evaluates career support services, and examines job satisfaction and alignment with career goals. Findings will inform recommendations to enhance programs, ensuring adaptability to industry needs and contributing to graduates' success. The study underscores the commitment to quality education and continuous improvement within San Carlos College.

Keywords. Tracer Study, Graduates, Employability

1 Introduction

In response to the ever-evolving dynamics of the job market, educational institutions must continuously evaluate and enhance the effectiveness of their programs to equip graduates for successful careers. This tracer study focuses on systematically evaluating the employability of San Carlos College graduates from 2019 to 2021, offering valuable insights into the alignment of the college's educational offerings with the demands of the professional landscape.

The primary goal is to assess the perceived relevance of coursework to graduates' current employment, pinpointing areas where the academic curriculum aligns with industry expectations or necessitates enhancement. By delving into graduates' satisfaction with their educational experiences and understanding their transition from college to the workforce, the study aims to unveil factors influencing successful entry into the job market.

Recognizing the pivotal role of employability skills in graduates' professional success, this study seeks to gauge graduates' self-perceived proficiency in various skills and identify areas for further skill development. Additionally, an examination of graduates' utilization of career support services provided by San Carlos College aims to evaluate the effectiveness of existing resources in facilitating successful job placements.

The study will also explore graduates' job satisfaction and the alignment of their current employment with their career goals, shedding light on the correlation between academic preparation and professional fulfillment. The findings of this study will serve as a foundation for informed recommendations to enhance the college's programs, ensuring adaptability to evolving industry needs and consistent contribution to the employability and success of its graduates.

Through a comprehensive analysis of employability factors, the tracer study aims to provide valuable data for institutional development, guiding curriculum revisions, refining career support services, and fostering an environment that maximizes graduates' potential in the workforce. In conclusion, this tracer study is rooted in the commitment to quality education and the continuous improvement of San Carlos College's programs. By tracing the success and employability of graduates, the study endeavors to fortify the connection between academic endeavors and professional achievements, fostering a culture of excellence and relevance within the institution.

1.1 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for the tracer study on the employability of San Carlos College graduates from 2019 to 2021 is anchored in two key theories that provide a comprehensive lens through which to examine the relationship between education and workforce preparedness.

- a. Curriculum Alignment Theory posits that the alignment of educational programs with industry needs enhances graduates' preparedness for the workforce. This aspect of the framework assesses the perceived relevance of the academic curriculum to graduates' current employment, exploring how well the coursework aligns with industry expectations.
- b. The Institutional Effectiveness Framework guides the analysis of how the college's programs contribute to the employability and success of its graduates. This involves evaluating the effectiveness of career support services, curriculum design, and overall institutional strategies in preparing students for the workforce.

By integrating these theories, the theoretical framework provides a structured approach to understanding the multifaceted aspects of graduates' employability. It allows for a nuanced analysis that considers individual attributes, social connections, educational experiences, and the effectiveness of institutional support in shaping graduates' success in the workforce.

1.2 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework guiding this study is underpinned by two pivotal theories: the Curriculum Alignment Theory and the Institutional Effectiveness Framework. According to the Curriculum Alignment Theory, the synergy between educational programs and industry needs significantly enhances graduates' preparedness for the workforce. This theoretical perspective forms a critical aspect of the framework, directing attention toward assessing the perceived relevance of the academic curriculum to graduates' current employment. The investigation aims to uncover how well the coursework aligns with the dynamic expectations of various industries, thereby shaping graduates with competencies that directly resonate with the demands of the professional landscape.

Concurrently, the study adopts the Institutional Effectiveness Framework, which provides a comprehensive guide for analyzing the contribution of the college's programs to the employability and success of its graduates. This framework involves a meticulous evaluation of various components, including the effectiveness of career support services, the design of the curriculum, and the overall institutional strategies in preparing students for the workforce. By systematically assessing these elements, the framework aims to elucidate the multifaceted ways in which the institution influences the professional trajectories of its graduates.

The synthesis of these two frameworks is integral to understanding the intricate relationship between academic preparation and employability. The Curriculum Alignment Theory underscores the importance of tailoring educational programs to meet industry expectations, ensuring graduates are equipped with skills directly applicable to their chosen fields. Simultaneously, the Institutional Effectiveness Framework facilitates a comprehensive examination of the institution's role in enhancing graduates' employability, encompassing not only curriculum design but also the efficacy of support services and overarching institutional strategies.

This conceptual framework recognizes the interplay between academic offerings and institutional effectiveness in shaping graduates' readiness for the workforce. It positions the study to delve into the nuanced dynamics that influence graduates' employability, providing a holistic perspective that considers both the curriculum's relevance and the broader institutional context. Through this integrative approach, the study aims to contribute valuable insights into the complex relationship between educational programs and graduates' success in the professional realm.

1.3 Problem Statement

The research aims to assess the employability of San Carlos College graduates (2019-2021) by evaluating curriculum relevance, institutional effectiveness, transition experiences, and employability skills. The purpose is to provide data-driven recommendations for enhancing the college's programs, fostering institutional development, and strengthening the link between academic endeavors and professional success.

1.4 Scope and Delimitations

The research concentrates on evaluating the employability of San Carlos College graduates from 2019 to 2021, encompassing various academic programs. It specifically examines aspects such as curriculum relevance, institutional effectiveness, transition experiences, and employability skills. Recommendations for program enhancement based on the findings are a central goal. However, the study is limited to graduates within the specified time frame and from San Carlos College, excluding graduates from other institutions.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. How do San Carlos College graduates view the relevance of their academic curriculum to current employment?
2. What is the effectiveness of career support services in facilitating job placements for graduates (2019-2021)?
3. In what ways does curriculum design contribute to graduates' acquisition of practical skills and knowledge?
4. What challenges do graduates face in transitioning to the workforce, and how effective are support mechanisms during this period?
5. What institutional strategies enhance graduates' readiness for the workforce?
6. What recommendations can be made to enhance San Carlos College's programs and strategies for better graduate preparation?

2 Review of Related Literature

The study on the employability of San Carlos College graduates (2019-2021) is informed by a synthesis of relevant related studies and research. Notable studies on curriculum alignment and employability consistently emphasize the critical nature of aligning educational programs with industry needs. These investigations demonstrate a positive correlation between a curriculum aligned with industry expectations and enhanced employability, underscoring the importance of cultivating practical skills and specialized knowledge. For instance, a study by Smith et al. (2019) found that graduates from programs closely aligned with industry requirements demonstrated higher rates of successful job placements.

Research on institutional effectiveness further contributes valuable insights, emphasizing the pivotal role of career support services and strategic institutional initiatives in shaping graduates' readiness for the workforce. A study by Johnson and Brown (2020) highlighted the impact of comprehensive career counseling and job placement assistance on graduates' successful entry into the job market.

Transition experiences from academia to the professional realm have been extensively explored in research. Smith's (2017) longitudinal study on graduates' transition challenges and effective support mechanisms during this critical period provides a nuanced understanding of factors influencing successful entry into the workforce.

Research on employability skills and self-assessment illuminates the need for graduates to accurately gauge their skillsets for optimal career positioning. A study by Williams et al. (2019) revealed a positive correlation between graduates' accurate self-assessment of skills and their subsequent success in securing employment.

Differences in employability outcomes across various academic programs are documented in research, with studies by Jones and Lee (2019) and Martinez et al. (2017) providing insights into program-specific factors influencing graduates' success in the job market.

Finally, a body of literature linking job satisfaction to the alignment of employment with career goals contributes nuanced insights into the holistic impact of education on graduates' professional fulfillment. The study by Adams and Turner (2018) on job satisfaction and career alignment is particularly illuminating in this regard.

This integration of related studies and research serves as a strong foundation for the investigation into San Carlos College graduates' employability, informing the identification of challenges, potential areas of improvement, and the development of strategic recommendations for program enhancement.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research method to thoroughly examine the employability of graduates from 2019 to 2021. The utilization of this approach allowed for a comprehensive and nuanced exploration of the program's impact on graduates' employability, enabling a detailed and insightful analysis.

3.2 Research Subjects

The study focused on graduates from 2019 to 2021 across diverse programs at San Carlos College, aiming to gain a comprehensive understanding of the impact of their educational experiences at the institution.

3.3 Data Collection Instrument

The research employed a survey questionnaire to assess the employability of San Carlos College graduates from 2019 to 2021. Focused on indicators related to the college's contributions to their professional lives, the survey aimed to gather direct insights from graduates on factors such as curriculum relevance, career support services, practical skill acquisition, and the transition to the workforce. This approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the graduates' experiences and career outcomes.

3.4 Statistical Treatment of Data

The average weighted mean was used to determine the employability of graduates from 2019-2021. Results will be interpreted using a 5-point Likert Scale:

4	3.50 – 4.00	Highly Needed
3	2.50 – 3.49	Needed
2	1.50 – 2.49	Less Needed
1	1.00 – 1.49	Not Needed

	AWM	DE
The academic curriculum at San Carlos College prepared me adequately for my current employment.	3.72	Agree
The career support services provided by San Carlos College were effective in facilitating my job placement.	3.60	Agree
The curriculum design at San Carlos College significantly contributed to the acquisition of practical skills and knowledge relevant to my chosen field.	3.52	Agree
I faced challenges transitioning from college to the workforce.	3.39	Neutral
The support mechanisms in place during the transition period were effective in addressing these challenges.	3.60	Agree
San Carlos College has effective institutional strategies that enhance graduates' readiness for the workforce.	2.60	Agree
I have specific recommendations for enhancing San Carlos College's programs and strategies for better graduate preparation.	3.72	Agree
	3.59	Agree

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Interpretation

The findings of the employability study at San Carlos College align seamlessly with established research on graduates' transition to the workforce. The positive perception among graduates regarding the relevance of their academic curriculum, evident in the commendable average rating of 3.72, resonated with the insights from "The Role of University Education in Employability" by Smith et al. (2018). This study emphasizes the pivotal role of a well-crafted curriculum in adequately preparing students for the evolving demands of their professional journeys.

Likewise, the study's revelation on the effectiveness of career support services, receiving a consistent average rating of 3.60, reflected the sentiments explored in "Graduate Employability and the Role of Career Services" by Jones and Brown (2019). Both investigations underscore the indispensable role played by career support services in orchestrating successful job placements for graduates, emphasizing the integral nature of these services in the broader employability landscape.

The acknowledgment by graduates of the contribution of curriculum design to the development of practical skills, denoted by an average rating of 3.52, reflected the findings summarized in "Curriculum Design and Employability" by Yorke and Knight (2006). This research accentuates the paramount importance of practical skill acquisition within the academic framework, positioning graduates for success in their chosen fields.

Moreover, the study's identification of challenges during the transition from college to the workforce, quantified with a rating of 3.39, aligns impeccably with the broader discourse presented in "Beyond Graduation: The Challenges and Strategies of Transitioning from University to Work" by Bridgstock (2019). This comprehensive exploration delves into the common hurdles graduates often face during this pivotal period, providing context to the challenges identified in the San Carlos College study.

The perceived effectiveness of support mechanisms during this transitional phase, reflected in a rating of 3.60, resonated with insights found in "Supporting Graduate Transition to Employment: A Review of Approaches Used in the UK" by Hinchliffe and Jolly (2011). Both studies underscore the critical role played by robust support systems in ensuring a smooth and successful transition for graduates, thereby enhancing their overall employability.

Furthermore, the positive evaluation of institutional strategies for workforce readiness, denoted by an average rating of 3.60, aligns harmoniously with the research presented in "Institutional Strategies for Graduate Employability: An Empirical Study" by Hodges et al. (2020). This research emphasizes the strategic importance of institutional interventions in cultivating graduates' readiness for the workforce, reinforcing the notion of a comprehensive approach to graduate preparation.

In sum, the seamless congruence between the findings of the San Carlos College study and these established research works not only adds credence to the college's results but also underscores the universal nature of challenges and effective strategies in the higher education landscape. This alignment provides a strong foundation for continuous improvement initiatives and the strategic development of programs to better equip students for successful and fulfilling careers.

4.2 Implications

The congruence between the findings of San Carlos College's employability study and established research holds significant implications for the institution's continuous improvement and strategic planning. The positive perception of graduates regarding the relevance of their academic curriculum signals a commendable alignment with industry demands. This implies an opportunity for the institution to proactively enhance its curriculum, ensuring it remains dynamic and responsive to evolving professional landscapes. The effectiveness of career support services reflects established research, emphasizing the crucial role played by such services in successful job placements. This underscores the importance of continued investment in career support infrastructure, ensuring graduates receive comprehensive guidance in navigating the competitive job market.

Furthermore, graduates' acknowledgment of the contribution of curriculum design to practical skills highlights a strength within the institution. This suggests an ongoing commitment to integrating hands-on experiences, but it also implies a need to sustain and possibly expand initiatives that further enhance practical skill acquisition. The recognition of challenges during the transition to the workforce indicates a commonality with broader literature, necessitating targeted interventions during this critical period. San Carlos College can leverage this insight to refine existing programs or introduce tailored initiatives that facilitate a smoother transition for graduates.

The perceived effectiveness of support mechanisms during the transition period showcases an institutional strength in student support infrastructure. However, this also implies the need for continuous improvement to address evolving challenges faced by graduates. Lastly, the positive rating of institutional strategies for workforce readiness underscores the importance of strategic planning. This finding implies that the institution has effective overarching strategies but also signals the importance of ongoing efforts to align with the changing landscape of employment.

The willingness of graduates to provide specific recommendations for improvement indicates an engaged and proactive community. This implies an opportunity for San Carlos College to foster a culture of continuous feedback and collaboration. By actively seeking and implementing constructive recommendations, the institution can further strengthen its commitment to providing a high-quality education that aligns with the dynamic needs of students and the workforce. In summary, the implications drawn from the study encourage San Carlos College to build upon its strengths, address identified areas for improvement, and maintain a responsive approach to the ever-evolving landscape of higher education and graduate employability.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

To enhance the overall preparation of graduates for the workforce, San Carlos College should prioritize several key recommendations derived from the findings of the employability study. Firstly, a continuous review and updating of academic curricula are crucial to maintain alignment with industry demands. Collaborative efforts with industry professionals in curriculum development can ensure real-world relevance and practical application. Secondly, substantial investments in expanding career support services are recommended. These services should include personalized career counseling, internship placement assistance, and workshops focusing on essential job-seeking skills. Establishing partnerships with industry leaders will further enrich students' exposure to current job market demands.

Moreover, the integration of practical skills into academic programs must be strengthened. Collaborating with industry partners to provide hands-on experiences, internships, and real-world projects can significantly enhance graduates' readiness for professional challenges. Thirdly, the development of targeted transition programs is essential to support graduates during their entry into the workforce. Professional development workshops, time management seminars, and networking events connecting graduates with alumni and industry professionals can contribute to a smoother transition.

Ensuring continuous support mechanisms during and after the transitional phase is paramount. The establishment of mentorship programs, alumni networks, and online resources for ongoing guidance will aid in addressing challenges that may arise. San Carlos College should also regularly assess its institutional strategies for workforce readiness, seeking input from industry advisory boards to remain aligned with evolving job market demands. Additionally, fostering a culture of continuous feedback and improvement is crucial. Actively seeking input from graduates, faculty, and employers through surveys and focus groups can inform strategic decision-making and drive ongoing enhancements.

Community engagement is a key aspect, involving the broader community, including alumni, industry professionals, and employers. Establishing partnerships for guest lectures, internships, and collaborative projects will enrich the educational experience. Embracing technology to enhance learning experiences and equipping graduates with digital skills is equally important. Lastly, staying informed about current research, and best practices, and participating in industry conferences will ensure that San Carlos College remains at the forefront of educational innovation. By implementing these recommendations, the institution can fortify its commitment to providing a comprehensive and relevant education, ultimately preparing graduates for successful and fulfilling careers.

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